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Fabrication of Porous Structure with 3D Printing Technology

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Abstract

The porous structure of electrodes in SOFCs is the key factor to improve its performance and the manufacturing method to control its design needs to be established. Additive manufacturing, so-called 3D printing technology can be a prospective method for the fabrication of electrodes of SOFCs. In this experiment, stereolithography, which is a form of 3D printing technology using UV-light with approximately 365nm wavelength and photocurable resin, is applied. The UV-light that goes through pinholes enables the production of multiple cylindrical objects at once. As a result, the objects and the empty spaces between them make the porous structure. Moreover, by changing the size and the number of holes and distance between them, the fabrication of electrodes with the desired microstructure can be expected.

Introduction

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are considered as prospective power generators because of their high efficiency and less emissions of CO₂ and other air pollutants such as NO_x and SO_x. These advantages increase the attention towards fuel cells and better improvement is required in terms of environmental load [1]. The microstructure (porosity) of an anode in SOFCs in particular, is responsible for the cell reaction, transfer phenomenon of hydrogen, water vapour and electron, and affects not only its performance but also durability. Especially the most important areas of solid oxide fuel cell anodes are the Triple Phase Boundary (TPB), where oxide ion meets hydrogen and chemical reaction occurs. It is necessary to produce the microstructure with multiple pores that transfer the fuel into electrochemical reaction zones (TPB) and let water vapour flow out smoothly. Therefore, the optimisation of the microstructure is crucial for the improvement of the performance [2]. A conventional method, which is wet processing, makes the irregular pore distribution by heat-treating the mixture of YSZ and NiO with pore formers is widely used [3]. However, this does not enable to control the distribution of gas channels and the size of each pore. Hence, an alternative way to realise the fabrication of microstructure of an anode, controlling its porosity, needs to be established.

Additive manufacturing, so called 3D printing technology is considered as a prospective method because of its flexibility to change the design although manufacturing time tends to be extremely long to improve the modeling accuracy [4]. The optimization of cell components including electrodes with Selective Laser Melting technology (SLM) proved the possibilities of better production of the porous structure in electrodes [5]. This research aims to fabricate electrodes with microstructure by adopting and advancing a type of 3D printing technology, especially stereolithography. In order to improve modeling accuracy while shortening manufacturing time, some basic experiments have been conducted. This paper, in particular, mentions objects, which are fabricated with an original 3D printer and consist of multi-cylinders and pores.

1. Apparatus and experimental method

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the 3D printer which was specifically designed for this research. UV-LED light irradiates a mixture of electrode powder and photo-curable resin in the pool. The glass plate is attached at the bottom of the pool in order for the light to pass through and reach the substrate, which is connected to the upper XYZ-stage. The UV-LED light with a wavelength of 365nm cures the resin on the surface of the substrate. For the light source, Omuron ZUV-H2OMC and ZUV-C2OH are used as a head and a controller respectively. For the optical system from the light source, whose output power is 540mW, to the pinhole plate, the compact microscope CM-30L2 made by Nikon with various lenses is used. Two types of pinhole plates (Fig. 3) : one with 16 (4×4) holes with 200μm diameter and the other one with 9 (3×3) holes with 300μm diameter are designed to fit in the 1.6mm diameter, which is the irradiation area when the objective lens is utilised. Electrode material is a mixture of NiO and YSZ, which are commonly used for anodes, and photo-curable resin, Henkel LOCTITE363 is added. Mixing ratio of the electrode material by volume is 5%, 10% and 20%. Though forming with the mixture of 5% and 20% are verified, 10% one is mainly employed because of its stability for forming.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the 3D printer

Figure 2 shows the position of the pinhole plate in the equipment. At the beginning, it was set under the glass plate at the bottom of the pool but it is put on the glass and covered with 50 μ m thickness coating film on it. This change decreases light scattering and enables to obtain the cylindrical objects, whose diameter is almost equal to pinholes'. Coating film prevents the formed objects from adhering to the glass not the substrate.

Fig. 2 Position of the pinhole plate

The space called “clearance” between the coating film and the substrate affects the height of the objects. The “clearance” is measured by the high precision laser displacement meter (OPTEx CDX-LE15) with accuracy of 0.1 μ m and controlled by the automatic XYZ-stage in 1 μ m increments in advance. The displacement meter is fixed at the same position as the optical system and replaced after completing measurement.

The pinhole plates are made of stainless and have a thickness of 100 μ m. As shown in Figure 3, Φ 200 μ m pinhole plate has 16 holes and Φ 300 μ m pinhole plate has 9 holes. The centre-to-centre distance between each hole is 300 μ m for Φ 200 μ m pinhole plate and 400 μ m for Φ 300 μ m pinhole plate. The number of pinholes is limited because of the

irradiation area, which is a circle with 1.6mm diameter when the objective lens of 10 magnification is applied. The irradiation area can be expanded by adopting another type of lens.

(a) $\Phi 200\mu\text{m}$ pinhole plate (b) $\Phi 300\mu\text{m}$ pinhole plate
Fig. 3 Pinhole plates

Figure 4 illustrates the procedure of forming multi-cylindrical objects and stacking layers. The UV-LED light goes through the pinholes and divided lights irradiate the mixture of electrode powder and photo-curable resin. After the irradiation, photo-curable resin is cured and cylindrical objects are formed on the surface of the substrate above. Once multi-objects of the 1st layer are formed, the substrate connected to the XYZ-stage moves up to make some space between the pinhole plate and the substrate so that the objects of the next layer are ready to be formed. By repeating this process, pores are obtained between each cylindrical object and layer and a mass with microstructure (porosity) is fabricated. This mass that consists of tiny cylindrical objects with gas channels can work as a part of a SOFC anode or an anode itself. In addition, by changing the design of the pinhole plate, it is possible to control porosity and pore distribution.

Fig. 4 Forming objects

2. Results and Discussion

Cure conditions

In order to determine the conditions that enable the perfect cure of the mixture of resin and electrode powders (mixture ratio 10%), experiments with $\Phi 300\mu\text{m}$ pinhole were conducted, changing the light source power and irradiation time. The range of the light source power is 50 to 100%. Figure 5 reveals the conditions where 9 cylindrical objects were successfully formed and where the formation failed or defect can be seen. As the results show, in order to form 9 cylindrical objects completely, at least 230 seconds duration is required with 80% light source power while only 100 and 80 seconds are the minimum irradiation times with 90% and 100% light source power respectively. Irradiation with 50 to 70% light source power for 240 seconds were unable to cure any cylindrical object.

Between 80% and 90% of the light source power, the cause of the rapid change in irradiation time required to obtain the perfect cure is not clear, it is currently under investigation.

Fig. 5 Relation between light source power and irradiation time

Multi-layer objects

Some samples of multi-layer objects were fabricated to demonstrate that the mass of cylindrical objects has the pores that can be gas channels of the electrode. These samples were successfully formed after the arrangement of automatic control system that controls the move of the substrate and the irradiation timing of the light.

Figure 6 shows the sample of 6-layer objects, which has 36 (6×6) cylindrical objects per layer. Each layer is about 2.4mm square and the average height of the whole mass is $142\mu\text{m}$. The calculated porosity is 54%, which is higher than the design value because each cylindrical object shrunk compared to the size of pinholes.

Figure 7 shows the sample of 10-layer objects. Each layer has 36 (6×6) cylindrical objects. The average height of the mass is $231\mu\text{m}$ and the distance between each object is $68\mu\text{m}$ on average.

(a) Colour image

(b) 3D image

Fig. 6 3D printed 6-layer objects

(a) Colour image

(b) 3D image

Fig. 7 3D printed 10-layer objects with microstructure

Figure 8 shows the optical microscopy image of the cross-section of multi-layer object. The gray area in the figure shows the void between layers. The gap seen at the centre of the image is surrounded by cured parts and has approximately 25µm height as designed. This proves that gas channels were successfully formed between each layer and enabled the fabrication of porous structure without the mixture of resin and electrode powder filling these gaps.

Fig. 8 Void between layers

3. Conclusions and future prospects

In this study, the original 3D printer enabled the production of multiple cylindrical objects and the mass with porous structure. The mixture of electrode powder and photo-curable resin was successfully cured with UV-LED light whose wavelength is 365µm. The size and

shape of each cylindrical object depends on those of pinholes. Also, the possibility of curing is affected by the light source power and the irradiation time. The mass with 6-layer and 10-layer objects demonstrate the formation of pores between each cylindrical object and layer.

In order to fabricate a decent-sized mass, the area in a plane direction needs to be extended. Further experiments will be done to increase layers and shorten the irradiation time for more rapid fabrication. Increase of the volume fraction of electrode material is also required. The final aim of this study is to produce more efficient and durable anodes for SOFCs that perform better than ones fabricated in a conventional way. This novel method using stereolithography will be an alternative technology because of its advantages, especially the flexibility to change or control the design of microstructure.

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